

RANGES OF UNITARY DIVISOR FUNCTIONS

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Abstract

For any real t , the unitary divisor function σ_t^* is the multiplicative arithmetic function defined by $\sigma_t^*(p^\alpha) = 1 + p^{\alpha t}$ for all primes p and positive integers α . Let $\overline{\sigma_t^*(\mathbb{N})}$ denote the topological closure of the range of σ_t^* . We calculate an explicit constant $\eta^* \approx 1.9742550$ and show that $\overline{\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})}$ is connected if and only if $r \in (0, \eta^*]$. We end with some open problems.

1. Introduction

For each $c \in \mathbb{C}$, the divisor function σ_c is defined by $\sigma_c(n) = \sum_{d|n} d^c$. Divisor functions, especially σ_1, σ_0 , and σ_{-1} , are among the most extensively-studied arithmetic functions [2, 10, 12]. For example, two very classical number-theoretic topics are the study of perfect numbers and the study of friendly numbers. A positive integer n is said to be *perfect* if $\sigma_{-1}(n) = 2$, and n is said to be *friendly* if there exists $m \neq n$ with $\sigma_{-1}(m) = \sigma_{-1}(n)$ [14]. Motivated by the very difficult problems related to perfect and friendly numbers, Laatsch [11] studied $\sigma_{-1}(\mathbb{N})$, the range of σ_{-1} . He showed that $\sigma_{-1}(\mathbb{N})$ is a dense subset of the interval $[1, \infty)$ and asked if $\sigma_{-1}(\mathbb{N})$ is in fact equal to the set $\mathbb{Q} \cap [1, \infty)$. Weiner [16] answered this question in the negative, showing that $(\mathbb{Q} \cap [1, \infty)) \setminus \sigma_{-1}(\mathbb{N})$ is also dense in $[1, \infty)$.

The author has studied ranges of divisor functions in a variety of contexts [4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. For example, it is shown in [4] that $\mathcal{N}(c) \rightarrow \infty$ as $\Re(c) \rightarrow -\infty$, where $\mathcal{N}(c)$ denotes the number of connected components of $\overline{\sigma_c(\mathbb{N})}$. Here, the overline denotes the topological closure. In [15], Sanna develops an algorithm that can be used to calculate $\overline{\sigma_{-r}(\mathbb{N})}$ when $r > 1$ is real and is known with sufficient precision. In addition, he proves that $\mathcal{N}(-r)$ is finite for such r . The author [5] has since extended this result, showing that $\mathcal{N}(c)$ is finite whenever $\Re(c) \leq 0$ and $c \neq 0$. Very recently, Zubrilina [17] has obtained asymptotic estimates for $\mathcal{N}(-r)$ when

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$r > 1$. She has also shown that there is no real number r such that $\mathcal{N}(r) = 4$.

In this paper, we study the close relatives of the divisor functions known as unitary divisor functions. A *unitary divisor* of an integer n is a divisor d of n such that $\gcd(d, n/d) = 1$. The unitary divisor function σ_c^* is defined by

$$\sigma_c^*(n) = \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ \gcd(d, n/d)=1}} d^c$$

(see, for example, [1], [3], or [9]). The function σ_c^* is multiplicative and satisfies $\sigma_c^*(p^\alpha) = 1 + p^{\alpha c}$ for all primes p and positive integers α .

If $t \in [-1, 0)$, then one may use the same argument that Laatsch employed in [11] in order to show that $\overline{\sigma_t^*(\mathbb{N})} = [1, \infty)$. In particular, $\overline{\sigma_t^*(\mathbb{N})}$ is connected if $t \in [-1, 0)$. On the other hand, $\overline{\sigma_t^*(\mathbb{N})}$ is a discrete disconnected set if $t \geq 0$ (indeed, in this case, $\sigma_t(\mathbb{N}) \cap [0, s]$ is finite for every $s > 0$). The purpose of this paper is to prove the following theorem. Let ζ denote the Riemann zeta function.

Theorem 1. *Let η^* be the unique number in the interval $(1, 2]$ that satisfies the equation*

$$\frac{2^{\eta^*} + 1}{2^{\eta^*}} \cdot \frac{(3^{\eta^*} + 1)^2}{3^{2\eta^*} + 1} = \frac{\zeta(\eta^*)}{\zeta(2\eta^*)}. \tag{1}$$

If $r \in \mathbb{R}$, then $\overline{\sigma_{-r}(\mathbb{N})}$ is connected if and only if $r \in (0, \eta^]$.*

Remark 1.1. In the process of proving Theorem 1, we will show that there is indeed a unique solution to the equation (1) in the interval $(1, 2]$.

In all that follows, we assume $r > 1$ and study $\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})$. We first observe that $\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N}) \subseteq [1, \zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)]$. This is because if $q_1^{\beta_1} \cdots q_v^{\beta_v}$ is the prime factorization of some positive integer, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{-r}^*(q_1^{\beta_1} \cdots q_v^{\beta_v}) &= \prod_{i=1}^v \sigma_{-r}^*(q_i^{\beta_i}) = \prod_{i=1}^v (1 + q_i^{-\beta_i r}) \leq \prod_{i=1}^v (1 + q_i^{-r}) < \prod_p (1 + p^{-r}) \\ &= \prod_p \left(\frac{1 - p^{-2r}}{1 - p^{-r}} \right) = \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}. \end{aligned}$$

It is straightforward to show that 1 and $\zeta(r)$ are elements of $\overline{\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})}$. Therefore, Theorem 1 tells us that $\overline{\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})} = [1, \zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)]$ if and only if $r \in (0, \eta^*]$.

2. Proofs

In what follows, let p_i denote the i^{th} prime number. Let $\nu_p(x)$ denote the exponent of the prime p appearing in the prime factorization of the integer x .

To start, we need the following technical yet simple lemma.

Lemma 1. *If $s, m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $s \leq m$, then $\frac{p_s^{2r} + 1}{p_s^{2r} + p_s^r} \leq \frac{p_m^{2r} + 1}{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}$ for all $r > 1$.*

Proof. Fix some $r > 1$, and write $h(x) = \frac{x^{2r} + 1}{x^{2r} + x^r}$. Then

$$h'(x) = \frac{r}{x(x^r + 1)^2} \left(x^r - 2 - \frac{1}{x^r} \right).$$

We see that $h(x)$ is increasing when $x \geq 3$. Hence, in order to complete the proof, it suffices to show that $h(2) \leq h(3)$. Let $f(s) = 2^s 3^{2s} + 2^{2s} + 2^s - (2^{2s} 3^s + 3^{2s} + 3^s)$. For $s \geq 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} f''(s) &= 18^s \log^2(18) + 4^s \log^2(4) + 2^s \log^2(2) - 12^s \log^2(12) - 9^s \log^2(9) - 3^s \log^2(3) \\ &> 18^s \log^2(18) - 12^s \log^2(12) - 9^s \log^2(9) > 18^s \log^2(18) - 2(12^s \log^2(12)). \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to verify that $18^s \log^2(18) - 2(12^s \log^2(12))$ is increasing in s for $s \geq 1$, so we obtain

$$f''(s) > 18 \log^2(18) - 2(12 \log^2(12)) > 0.$$

A simple calculation shows that $f'(1) > 0$, so it follows that $f'(s) > 0$ for all $s \geq 1$. Since $f(1) = 0$ and $r > 1$, we have $f(r) > 0$. Equivalently, $2^{2r} 3^r + 3^{2r} + 3^r < 2^r 3^{2r} + 2^{2r} + 2^r$. It follows that $(2^{2r} + 1)(3^{2r} + 3^r) < (2^{2r} + 2^r)(3^{2r} + 1)$. This shows that $\frac{2^{2r} + 1}{2^{2r} + 2^r} < \frac{3^{2r} + 1}{3^{2r} + 3^r}$, which completes the proof. $\square$

The following theorem replaces the question of whether or not $\overline{\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})}$ is connected with a question concerning infinitely many inequalities. The advantage in doing this is that we will further reduce this problem to the consideration of a finite list of inequalities in Theorem 3. Recall from the introduction that $\overline{\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})}$ is connected if and only if it is equal to the interval $[1, \zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)]$.

Theorem 2. *If $r > 1$, then $\overline{\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})} = [1, \zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)]$ if and only if*

$$\frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} \leq \prod_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r} \right)$$

for all positive integers m .

Proof. First, suppose that $\frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} \leq \prod_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r} \right)$ for all positive integers m .

We will show that the range of $\log \sigma_{-r}^*$ is dense in $[0, \log(\zeta(r)/\zeta(2r))]$, which will then imply that the range of σ_{-r}^* is dense in $[1, \zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)]$. Fix some

$$x \in (0, \log(\zeta(r)/\zeta(2r))).$$

We will construct a sequence $(C_i)_{i=1}^\infty$ of elements of the range of $\log \sigma_{-r}^*$ that converges to x . First, let $C_0 = 0$. For each positive integer n , if $C_{n-1} < x$, let $C_n = C_{n-1} + \log(1 + p_n^{-\alpha_n r})$, where α_n is the smallest positive integer that satisfies $C_{n-1} + \log(1 + p_n^{-\alpha_n r}) \leq x$. If $C_{n-1} = x$, simply set $C_n = C_{n-1} = x$. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $C_n \in \log \sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})$. Indeed, if $C_n \neq C_{n-1}$, then

$$C_n = \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 + p_i^{-\alpha_i r}) = \log \left(\prod_{i=1}^n (1 + p_i^{-\alpha_i r}) \right) = \log \sigma_{-r}^* \left(\prod_{i=1}^n p_i^{\alpha_i} \right).$$

If, however, $C_n = C_{n-1} = x$, then we may let l be the smallest positive integer such that $C_l = x$ and show, in the same manner as above, that

$$C_n = C_l = \log \sigma_{-r}^* \left(\prod_{i=1}^l p_i^{\alpha_i} \right).$$

Let us write $\gamma = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} C_n$. Note that γ exists and that $\gamma \leq x$ because the sequence $(C_i)_{i=1}^\infty$ is nondecreasing and bounded above by x . If we can show that $\gamma = x$, then we will be done. Therefore, let us assume instead that $\gamma < x$.

We have $C_n = C_{n-1} + \log(1 + p_n^{-\alpha_n r})$ for all positive integers n . Write $D_n = \log(1 + p_n^{-r}) - \log(1 + p_n^{-\alpha_n r})$ and $E_n = \sum_{i=1}^n D_i$. As

$$\begin{aligned} x + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_n &> \gamma + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (C_n + E_n) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 + p_i^{-\alpha_i r}) + \sum_{i=1}^n D_i \right) \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^n \log(1 + p_i^{-r}) = \log(\zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)), \end{aligned}$$

we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_n > \log(\zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)) - x$. Therefore, we may let m be the smallest positive integer such that $E_m > \log(\zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)) - x$. If $\alpha_m = 1$ and $m > 1$, then $D_m = 0$. This forces $E_{m-1} = E_m > \log(\zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)) - x$, contradicting the minimality of m . If $\alpha_m = 1$ and $m = 1$, then $0 = E_m > \log(\zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)) - x$, which is also a contradiction since we originally chose $x < \log(\zeta(r)/\zeta(2r))$. Consequently, $\alpha_m > 1$. Due to the way we defined C_m and α_m , we have

$$C_{m-1} + \log(1 + p_n^{-(\alpha_m - 1)r}) > x.$$

Hence,

$$\log(1 + p_n^{-(\alpha_m - 1)r}) - \log(1 + p_n^{-\alpha_m r}) > x - C_m.$$

Using our original assumption that $\frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} \leq \prod_{i=m+1}^\infty \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r}\right)$, we have

$$\log\left(\frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1}\right) \leq \sum_{i=m+1}^\infty \log\left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r}\right) = \log\left(\frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}\right) - E_m - C_m$$

$$< x - C_m < \log \left(1 + p_n^{-(\alpha_m - 1)r} \right) - \log \left(1 + p_n^{-\alpha_m r} \right) = \log \left(\frac{p_m^{\alpha_m r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{\alpha_m r} + 1} \right).$$

Thus,

$$\frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} < \frac{p_m^{\alpha_m r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{\alpha_m r} + 1}.$$

Rewriting this inequality, we get $p_m^{2r} + p_m^{(\alpha_m + 1)r} < p_m^{3r} + p_m^{\alpha_m r}$. Dividing through by $p_m^{\alpha_m r}$ yields $p_m^{(2 - \alpha_m)r} + p_m^r < 1 + p_m^{(3 - \alpha_m)r}$, which is impossible since $\alpha_m \geq 2$. This contradiction proves that $\gamma = x$, so $\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N}) = [1, \zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)]$.

To prove the converse, suppose there exists some positive integer m such that

$$\frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} > \prod_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r} \right).$$

We may write this inequality as

$$\frac{p_m^{2r} + 1}{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r} < \prod_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r} \right)^{-1}. \tag{2}$$

Fix a positive integer N . If $\nu_{p_s}(N) = 1$ for all $s \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$, then

$$\sigma_{-r}^*(N) \geq \prod_{s=1}^m \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_s^r} \right) = \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)} \prod_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r} \right)^{-1}.$$

On the other hand, if $\nu_{p_s}(N) \neq 1$ for some $s \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$, then $\sigma_{-r}^*(p_s^{\nu_{p_s}(N)}) \leq 1 + \frac{1}{p_s^{2r}}$. This implies that

$$\sigma_{-r}^*(N) \leq \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_s^{2r}} \right) \prod_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq s}}^m \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r} \right) = \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)} \frac{1 + p_s^{-2r}}{1 + p_s^{-r}} = \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)} \frac{p_s^{2r} + 1}{p_s^{2r} + p_s^r}$$

in this case. Using Lemma 1, we have

$$\sigma_{-r}^*(N) \leq \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)} \frac{p_m^{2r} + 1}{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}.$$

As N was arbitrary, we have shown that there is no element of the range of σ_{-r}^* in the interval

$$\left(\frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)} \frac{p_m^{2r} + 1}{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}, \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)} \prod_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r} \right)^{-1} \right).$$

This interval is a gap in the range of σ_{-r}^* , because of the inequality (2). □

As mentioned above, we wish to reduce the task of checking the infinite collection of inequalities given in Theorem 2 to that of checking finitely many inequalities. We do so in Theorem 3, the proof of which requires the following lemma.

Lemma 2. *If $j \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$, then $\frac{p_{j+1}}{p_j} < \sqrt[3]{2}$.*

Proof. In [13], it is shown that $\frac{p_{j+1}}{p_j} \leq \frac{6}{5} < \sqrt[3]{2}$ for all $j \geq 10$. We easily verify the cases $j = 5, 7, 8$ by hand. □

Theorem 3. *If $r \in (1, 3]$, then $\overline{\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})} = [1, \zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)]$ if and only if*

$$\frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} \leq \prod_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r}\right)$$

for all $m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$.

Proof. Let

$$F(m, r) = \frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} \prod_{i=1}^m \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r}\right)$$

so that the inequality $\frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} \leq \prod_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r}\right)$ is equivalent to $F(m, r) \leq \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}$.

Let $r \in (1, 3]$. By Theorem 2, it suffices to show that if $F(m, r) \leq \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}$ for all $m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$, then $F(m, r) \leq \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}$ for all $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Therefore, assume that r is such that $F(m, r) \leq \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}$ for all $m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$.

We will show that $F(m + 1, r) > F(m, r)$ for all $m \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$. This will show that $(F(m, r))_{m=10}^{\infty}$ is an increasing sequence. As $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} F(m, r) = \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}$, it will then follow that $F(m, r) < \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}$ for all integers $m \geq 10$. Furthermore, we will see that $F(5, r) < F(6, r) \leq \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}$ and $F(7, r) < F(8, r) < F(9, r) \leq \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}$, which will complete the proof.

Let $m \in \mathbb{N} \setminus \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$. By Lemma 2, $\frac{p_{m+1}}{p_m} < \sqrt[3]{2} \leq \sqrt[3]{2}$. This shows that $p_{m+1}^r < 2p_m^r$, implying that $2p_m^{2r} > p_m^r p_{m+1}^r$. Therefore,

$$2p_m^{2r} + 2 > p_m^r p_{m+1}^r + \frac{p_m^r}{p_{m+1}^r} - p_{m+1}^r - \frac{1}{p_{m+1}^r} = \frac{(p_m^r - 1)(p_{m+1}^{2r} + 1)}{p_{m+1}^r}.$$

Multiplying each side of this inequality by $\frac{p_{m+1}^r}{(p_{m+1}^{2r} + 1)(p_m^{2r} + 1)}$ and adding 1 to each side, we get

$$1 + \frac{2p_{m+1}^r}{p_{m+1}^{2r} + 1} > 1 + \frac{p_m^r - 1}{p_m^{2r} + 1},$$

which we may write as

$$\frac{(p_{m+1}^r + 1)^2}{p_{m+1}^{2r} + 1} > \frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1}.$$

Finally, we get

$$\begin{aligned} F(m + 1, r) &= \frac{p_{m+1}^{2r} + p_{m+1}^r}{p_{m+1}^{2r} + 1} \prod_{i=1}^{m+1} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r}\right) = \frac{(p_{m+1}^r + 1)^2}{p_{m+1}^{2r} + 1} \prod_{i=1}^m \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r}\right) \\ &> \frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} \prod_{i=1}^m \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r}\right) = F(m, r). \end{aligned} \quad \square$$

Now, let

$$V_m(r) = \log \left(\frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} \right) - \sum_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \log \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r} \right).$$

Equivalently, $V_m(r) = \log(F(m, r)) - \log \left(\frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)} \right)$, where F is the function defined in the proof of Theorem 3. Observe that

$$\frac{p_m^{2r} + p_m^r}{p_m^{2r} + 1} \leq \prod_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i^r} \right)$$

if and only if $V_m(r) \leq 0$. If we let $J_m(r) = \sum_{i=m+1}^{m+6} \frac{1}{p_i^r + 1} - \frac{p_m^{2r} - 2p_m^r - 1}{(p_m^r + 1)(p_m^{2r} + 1)}$, then we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} J_m(r) = \frac{p_m^r((p_m^r - 1)^4 - 12p_m^{2r}) \log p_m}{(p_m^r + 1)^2(p_m^{2r} + 1)^2} - \sum_{i=m+1}^{m+6} \frac{p_i^r \log p_i}{(p_i^r + 1)^2}.$$

It is not difficult to verify that $\frac{p_m^r((p_m^r - 1)^4 - 12p_m^{2r}) \log p_m}{(p_m^r + 1)^2(p_m^{2r} + 1)^2} \geq -1$ for all $r \in [1, 2]$ and $m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$. Therefore, when $r \in [1, 2]$ and $m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$, we have

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} J_m(r) \geq -1 - \sum_{i=m+1}^{m+6} \frac{p_i^r \log p_i}{(p_i^r + 1)^2} \geq -1 - \sum_{i=m+1}^{m+6} \frac{\log p_i}{p_i^r} > -7.$$

Numerical calculations show that $J_m(r) > \frac{1}{400}$ for all $m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$ and

$$r \in \left\{ 1 + \frac{n}{2800} : n \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2800\} \right\}.$$

Because each function J_m is continuous in r for $r \in [1, 2]$, we see that

$$J_m(r) > \frac{1}{400} - 7 \left(\frac{1}{2800} \right) = 0$$

for all $r \in [1, 2]$ and $m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$.

We introduced the functions J_m so that we could write

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} V_m(r) = \sum_{i=m+1}^{\infty} \frac{\log p_i}{p_i^r + 1} - \frac{(p_m^{2r} - 2p_m^r - 1) \log p_m}{(p_m^r + 1)(p_m^{2r} + 1)} > (\log p_m) J_m(r) > 0$$

for all $m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$ and $r \in [1, 2]$. A quick numerical calculation shows that $V_2(1.5) < 0 < V_2(2)$, so the function V_2 has exactly one root, which we will call η^* , in the interval $(1, 2]$. Further calculations show that $V_m(2) < 0$ for all $m \in \{1, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$. Hence, $V_m(r) \leq 0$ for all $m \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 9\}$ and $r \in (1, \eta^*]$. By Theorem 3, this means that if $r \in (1, 2]$, then $\overline{\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})} [1, \zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)]$ if and only if $r \leq \eta^*$.

Next, note that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} V_2(r) &= \sum_{i=3}^{\infty} \frac{\log p_i}{p_i^r + 1} - \frac{(3^{2r} - 2 \cdot 3^r - 1) \log 3}{(3^{2r} + 1)(3^r + 1)} > -\frac{(3^{2r} - 2 \cdot 3^r - 1) \log 3}{(3^{2r} + 1)(3^r + 1)} \\ &> -\frac{(3^{2r} + 1) \log 3}{(3^{2r} + 1)(3^r + 1)} \geq -\frac{\log 3}{3^2 + 1} > -1.1 \end{aligned}$$

for all $r \in [2, 3]$. Let $A = \left\{ 2 + \frac{n}{400} : n \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 400\} \right\}$. With a computer program, one may verify that $V_2(r) > 0.003$ for all $r \in A$. Because V_2 is continuous, this shows that $V_2(r) > 0.003 - 1.1 \left(\frac{1}{400} \right) > 0$ for all $r \in [2, 3]$. Consequently, $\overline{\sigma_{-r}^*(\mathbb{N})} \neq [1, \zeta(r)/\zeta(2r)]$ if $r \in [2, 3]$.

We are now in a position to prove Theorem 1. Note that the equation defining η^* in the statement of this theorem is simply a rearrangement of the equation $V_2(\eta^*) = 0$. Therefore, we have shown that the theorem is true for $r \in (1, 3]$. In order to prove the theorem for $r > 3$, it suffices (by Theorem 3) to show that $F(1, r) > \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}$ for all $r > 3$. If $r > 3$, then

$$\begin{aligned} F(1, r) &= \frac{(2^r + 1)^2}{2^{2r} + 1} = \frac{2^{2r} + 2^{r+1} + 1}{2^{2r} + 1} > \frac{2^{2r} + 2^r + \frac{2^{r+1}}{r-1}}{2^{2r} + 1} = \frac{1 + \frac{1}{2^r} + \frac{1}{(r-1)2^{r-1}}}{1 + \frac{1}{2^{2r}}} \\ &> \frac{1 + \frac{1}{2^r} + \frac{1}{(r-1)2^{r-1}}}{\zeta(2r)} = \frac{1 + \frac{1}{2^r} + \int_2^{\infty} x^{-r} dx}{\zeta(2r)} > \frac{\zeta(r)}{\zeta(2r)}. \end{aligned}$$

3. Future Directions

Let $\mathcal{N}^*(t)$ denote the number of connected components of $\overline{\sigma_t^*(\mathbb{N})}$. It would be interesting to obtain analogues of Zubrilina's results [17] by finding asymptotic estimates for $\mathcal{N}^*(-r)$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$. Let

$$E_m^* = \{t \in \mathbb{R} : \mathcal{N}^*(t) = m\}.$$

Theorem 1 tells us that $E_1^* = [-\eta^*, 0)$. The sets E_m^* are the natural unitary analogues of the sets E_m defined in [5, Section 4]. Continuing the analogy, we say a positive integer m is a *unitary Zubrilina number* if $E_m^* = \emptyset$ (the name comes from Zubrilina's result that $E_4 = \emptyset$). We do not have any specific examples of unitary Zubrilina numbers, but we still make the following conjectures.

Conjecture 1. There are infinitely many unitary Zubrilina numbers.

Conjecture 2. For $r > 1$, $\mathcal{N}^*(-r)$ is monotonically increasing as a function of r .

Note that Conjecture 2 implies that the sets E_m^* are intervals.

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References

- [1] K. Alladi, On arithmetic functions and divisors of higher order, *J. Austral. Math. Soc. Ser. A.* **23** (1997), 9–27.
- [2] T. M. Apostol, *Introduction to Analytic Number Theory*, Springer-Verlag, 1976.
- [3] E. Cohen, Arithmetical functions associated with the unitary divisors of an integer, *Math. Z.* **74** (1960), 66–80.
- [4] C. Defant, Complex divisor functions, *Anal. Geom. Number Theory* **1** (2016), 22–48.
- [5] C. Defant, Connected components of complex divisor functions, arXiv:1711.04244.
- [6] C. Defant, On ranges of variants of the divisor functions that are dense, *Int. J. Number Theory* **11** (2015), 1905–1912.
- [7] C. Defant, On the density of ranges of generalized divisor functions, *Notes on Number Theory and Discrete Mathematics* **21** (2015), 80–87.
- [8] C. Defant, On the density of ranges of generalized divisor functions with restricted domains, *Unif. Distrib. Theory* **10** (2015), 19–33.
- [9] R. K. Guy, *Unsolved Problems in Number Theory*, Springer-Verlag, 1981.

- [10] G. H. Hardy, P. V. Seshu Aiyar, and B. M. Wilson, *Collected Papers of Srinivasa Ramanujan*, Cambridge: University Press, 1927.
- [11] R. Laatsch, Measuring the abundancy of integers, *Math. Mag.* **59** (1986), 84–92.
- [12] D. S. Mitrinović, J. Sándor, and B. Crstici, *Handbook of Number Theory, Mathematics and its Applications, Vol. 351, Chapter III*, Kluwer Academic Publishers Group, Dordrecht, 1996.
- [13] J. Nagura, On the interval containing at least one prime number, *Proc. Japan Acad.* **28** (1952), 177–181.
- [14] P. Pollack and C. Pomerance, Some problems of Erdős on the sum-of-divisors function. *Trans. Amer. Math. Soc.* **3** (2016), 1–26.
- [15] C. Sanna, On the closure of the image of the generalized divisor function, *Unif. Distrib. Theory* **12** (2017), 77–90.
- [16] P. A. Weiner, The abundancy ratio, a measure of perfection, *Math. Mag.* **73** (2000), 307–310.
- [17] N. Zubrilina, On the number of connected components of ranges of divisor functions, arXiv:1711.02871.